

Risk factors for major postoperative complications in people with chronic spinal cord injury/disorder and stage III and IV pressure injuries

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SHORT SUMMARY

Pressure injuries (PIs) are the second most common secondary condition associated with spinal cord injury or disorder (SCI/D). Although the surgical management of stage III and IV PI using treatment approaches such as the Basel Decubitus Approach (BDA) can be very effective, major complication rates still reach up to 20%. The thesis aims to identify modifiable risk factors associated with major postoperative complications in the treatment of stage III and IV PI in people with SCI/D. The research focused on three aspects: firstly, the treatment approaches addressing risk factors; secondly, single risk factors associated with major postoperative complications; and thirdly, the prediction of major postoperative complications based on the combination of different risk factors. The main findings of the thesis were that stage IV PI, the absence of osteomyelitis, low C-reactive protein (CRP), low renal function, normal hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c), low calcium, low sodium, low vitamin B12 and high vitamin D were positively associated with major postoperative complications in a setting where the BDA is implemented. These factors should therefore be considered to further improve the BDA when treating stage III and IV PI.

LIST OF ABBREVIATION

ASIA/ISCoS	American Spinal Injury Association/International Spinal Cord Society
AIS	Abbreviated Injury Scale
BDA	Basel Decubitus Approach
BMI	Body Mass Index
CRP	C-Reactive Protein
CSCM	Consortium for Spinal Cord Medicine
DELBI	German Instrument for Methodological Guideline Appraisal
DMGP	German-Speaking Medical Society for Paraplegiology
e.g.	Exempli Gratia
EPUAP	European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel
ESR	Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate
et al.	Et Alia
eGFR	Estimated Glomerular Filtration Rate
HbA1c	Hemoglobin AC1c
HDL cholesterol	High Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol
INR	International Normalized Ratio
IQR	Interquartile Range
ISNCSCI	International Standards for Neurological Classification of Spinal Cord Injury
LASSO	Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator
LDL cholesterol	Low Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol
NRS	Nutritional Risk Screening
OSAS	Obstructive Sleep Apnea Syndrome
OM	Osteomyelitis
Ph.D.	Doctor of Philosophy

PI(s)	Pressure Injury/Pressure Injuries
PICOS	Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, Study Design
PPPIA	Pan Pacific Pressure Injury Alliance
PRISMA-ScR	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Extensions for Scoping Reviews
SCI/D	Spinal Cord Injury or Disorder
SNST	Spinal Nutrition Screening Tool
STROBE	Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology
TIME	Tissue, Infection/Inflammation Control, Moisture Imbalance and Epithelial Advancement
TSH	Thyroid Stimulating Hormone
UK	United Kingdom
USA	United States of America
UTI	Urinary Tract Infection

CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

Pressure injuries in people with SCI/D

People with spinal cord injury or disorder (SCI/D) are at an increased risk of developing pressure injuries (PI). This is due to the lack of sensation and immobility in this population [1-3]. A PI is a localized damage to the skin and underlying tissues caused by intense and prolonged pressure or a combination of pressure and shear forces [4, 5]. Intense pressure over a short period of time can cause the same damage as less intense pressure over a longer period of time [6].

PIs usually occur over bony prominences [5]. When soft tissue is compressed between the bone and a hard surface, blood flow to the tissue is blocked and necrosis can occur [2, 6]. The onset of necrosis is one to two hours dependent on the individual pressure tolerance [6]. In people with SCI/D, approximately 70% of the PIs are located in the pelvic region over the ischium, trochanter and sacrum/coccyx [7-11]. The ischial tuberosities are at high risk of ulceration when sitting in a wheelchair, the sacrum when lying on the back and the trochanters when lying on the side [5].

People with SCI/D should regularly relieve pressure for more than two minutes every 15-30 minutes when sitting in a wheelchair and every two hours when lying on a mattress [3, 7]. Another prevention strategy is to minimize external conditions that contribute to the development of PIs in addition to excessive pressure such as shear, friction and maceration [6]. This can be achieved through careful transfers, control of spasticity and control of bladder and bowel incontinence [6]. In addition, people with SCI/D should check the skin over bony prominences at least daily [6]. Despite good education and optimized prevention strategies, PIs are the second most frequent complication in people with SCI/D [12]. The lifetime incidence of at least one PI in people with SCI/D is up to 85%, and 30% of these are expected to experience recurrent PIs [5, 13-17]. Furthermore, reported prevalence rates of PIs among people with SCI/D living in the community vary from 17 to 33%, generally within a one-year reporting period [18].

PIs are a life-threatening secondary condition with a high risk of infection, osteomyelitis, sepsis and death [5]. They restrict the individual's participation in daily activities and community integration [5]. PIs are therefore a major burden on the health and quality of life of those affected [2]. Moreover, PIs generate the highest cost among all SCI/D complications [12, 19]. In the USA, they account for approximately \$ 1.4 billion [18].

Treatment of stage III and IV PIs in people with SCI/D

PI classification

The treatment of PIs in individuals with SCI/D depends on the stage of the PI [11, 20]. According to the guideline of the European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel, the National Pressure Injury Advisory Panel and Pan Pacific Pressure Injury Alliance (hereafter referred to as EPUAP), PIs are categorized into four stages of severity (Figure 1) [2]. In a stage I PI, the skin is still intact with a localized area of non-blanchable erythema [2]. Stage II means a partial-thickness skin loss with exposed dermis [2]. Stage I and II PIs are mostly treated conservatively [11, 20]. In stage III, there is a full-thickness skin loss [2]. If the fascia, muscle, tendon, ligament, cartilage or bone is exposed through full-thickness tissue loss, stage IV is entered [2]. Stage III and IV PIs are also called deep PIs [2]. They are usually associated with large amounts of tissue loss and can take months to years to heal by conservative means [11, 20]. Surgical management is therefore recommended for stage III and IV PIs, as the healing is much faster [11, 20].

Figure 1. Stage I-IV PI. Copyright by Swiss Paraplegic Center. Reprinted with permission.

Surgical management of stage III and IV PIs in people with SCI/D

Surgical management of stage III and IV PIs includes debridement and surgical reconstruction [11, 21]. During debridement necrotic tissue is removed in order to maintain a vital wound edge and wound bed [21]. Wound healing requires a clean wound, free of necrosis and debris before further intervention [21]. After debridement, surgical closure of

the PI is performed [5, 11, 21]. There are several surgical techniques for PI closure [11]. Most commonly flap surgery is used [11]. The aim of a flap surgery is to cover the pressurized area with high quality tissue and to keep the scar course outside the maximum pressure zone as far as possible [21]. The surgical procedure consists of ulcer excision, bone necrosectomy and reconstruction [10]. In contrast to the general population, people with SCI/D have an increased risk of recurrent PI [6]. Therefore, the possibility of recurrence must also be considered when planning the incision [21].

Surgical management can be very effective for deep PIs [11]. However, postoperative complications such as wound dehiscence, bleeding, hematoma, recurrence, partial necrosis or total flap necrosis occur in around 30% and 50% [22-25]. They increase the length of hospital stay and costs [26]. Postoperative complications are divided into minor and major complications [27]. Minor complications are classified by Dindo et al. as complications that can be treated conservatively [27]. In contrast, major complications require surgical intervention or intensive care management [27]. Major complications occur in approximately 16% of flap surgeries in people with SCI/D and stage III and IV PI [22, 26, 28].

The success of a flap surgery depends on preoperative conditioning, surgical technique and postoperative care [11]. In general, there is little research on the clinical management of stage III and IV PI in people with SCI/D [1]. In addition, the research in this field is insufficient due to low methodological studies with small sample sizes. The reason for this could be not only the complexity of PI treatment, but also the complexity of the SCI/D condition. This is because people with SCI/D often have several comorbidities that also need to be considered when treating PIs [2]. It is known, however, that the health condition of stage III and IV PIs requires a multi-layered coordinated involvement of different disciplines and professions, focusing not only on the wound, but also on the individual's biologic, psychologic and social system [11, 13, 24, 25, 29]. Therefore, multidisciplinary treatment approaches have been developed [19, 24]. These treatment approaches aim to address factors associated with postoperative complications in order to reduce complication rates, length of hospital stay, treatment costs and recurrences after hospital discharge [19, 24].

The Basel Decubitus Approach

At the Swiss Paraplegic Centre, the Basel Decubitus Approach (BDA) is applied for the surgical management of deep PIs in individuals with SCI/D (Figure 2). It is a multidisciplinary treatment approach based on the bio-psycho-social model of the

International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health of the World Health Organization, which considers medical, psychological and social aspects [30]. In 1992, Lüscher and colleagues mentioned the BDA for the first time [31]. The approach was then modified based on years of experiences [9, 24, 32]. Moreover, the different components of the BDA have been re-evaluated in several international consensus conferences [24]. The BDA consists of the following treatment elements: PI classification according to the EPUAP, pressure relief, treatment of infection, wound conditioning and skin management, treatment of risk factors and nutritional optimization as well as prevention of secondary complication and education [2, 24]. Moreover, the approach includes the milestones: debridement, flap surgery, suture removal and mobilization in wheelchair (Figure 2) [24].

Figure 2. Overview of the BDA.

Overall goal and methodology

Currently, it is unknown what treatment approaches exist in practice worldwide and what risk factors they consider. Furthermore, only few studies have focused on postoperative complications in the treatment of stage III and IV PIs in people with SCI/D. According to these studies, hemoglobin AC1c (HbA1c) below 6%, previous same-site flap failure, ischial

PI, younger or older age, overweight or underweight, albumin below 3.5 g/dl, presence of osteomyelitis, ASIA A and male sex (<3.5 g/dl) were associated with postoperative complications [26, 32-34]. The studies observed only stage IV PI, considered only one type of complication, included minor complications, or considered acute SCI/D. Although, there are some studies observing complications in the treatment of deep PIs in people with SCI/D, currently, limited information is available on modifiable risk factors associated with major postoperative complications in the chronic phase of SCI/D [26, 32-34].

Therefore, the overall goal of the thesis was to identify modifiable risk factors for major postoperative complications that need to be considered when treating stage III and IV PIs in people with chronic SCI/D. This knowledge is needed to further improve treatment approaches, reduce major postoperative complications and ultimately improve patients' quality of life. The Ph.D. project was therefore embedded in a larger project. The PI project of the Swiss Paraplegic Research aimed to adapt the BDA based on the findings of the Ph.D.

In contrast to the literature, in this thesis, we decided to focus only on major complications and excluded minor complications [27]. Having two clearly separated cohort groups, major complications and no complication, avoids potential confounding by minor complications. Previous studies also included individuals having a PI during initial rehabilitation after the onset of SCI/D. In this thesis, we only wanted to focus on chronic SCI/D. This is because individuals with a hospital acquired PI during initial rehabilitation have a different treatment focus and health status compared to individuals with chronic SCI/D suffering from PI. Although, deep PIs can occur in any region of the body, we decided to focus on the most commonly area for PI: ischium, trochanter and sacrum/coccyx [11]. Furthermore, modifiable risk factors are of particular interest to the thesis. These risk factors can be addressed and adapted during the treatment. However, we also observe non-modifiable risk factors. This is because non-modifiable risk factors cannot be ignored when predicting postoperative complications.

As a first step, we wanted to provide a situational analysis of existing treatment approaches and possible risk factors already addressed by treatment elements in the management of stage III and IV PIs in people with SCI/D. The aims of the first study were to identify multidisciplinary treatment approaches, to describe the included treatment elements that address risk factors and to describe the effectiveness of the approaches. As a systematic review was not possible due to the lack of randomized control trials in this field, we decided to conduct a scoping review using PubMed and Medline. This scoping review was a first step of the larger PI project of the Swiss Paraplegic Research to compare the BDA with

other treatment approaches and to obtain information on whether the approach needs further improvement, e.g. due to missing treatment of a risk factor.

Based on these findings, we analysed routinely collected clinical data. We conducted an exploratory retrospective cohort study using likelihood ratio tests to identify modifiable risk factors associated with major complications. The aims of the second study were to describe differences in patients', PI and surgery characteristics between people with and without major complications after flap surgery and to identify modifiable risk factors that can be addressed during treatment. We performed likelihood ratio tests, which are commonly used test in clinical research for dependent data and to analyze variables with more than two categories [35]. The data consisted of variables with three or even four categories, e.g. lesion level, AIS grade and localization of PI. Furthermore, we had dependent data because some individuals had multiple PI treatments. Therefore, we performed computed global p-values using likelihood ratio tests and adjusted for clustering of PIs in individuals.

In the third project, we wanted to combine information from several different risk factors for major complications after flap surgery in people with SCI/D and stage III and IV PI. This was because, based on the second study, we still did not know how the risk factors influence each other. The objective of the last study was to predict the risk of major complications after flap surgery in people with SCI/D and stage III and IV PI. The aims were to generate a risk prediction model for major complications after flap surgery in people with SCI/D and stage III and IV PI, to identify risk factors associated with major complications after flap surgery and to identify modifiable risk factors that can be addressed during treatment. We decided to do a mixed-effects logistic Bayesian least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO) model because it uses a shrinkage penalty. The LASSO model results in a sparser model with fewer features having non-zero coefficients than the ordinary logistic regression. This can improve the interpretability of the model and reduce overfitting. Furthermore, Bayesian LASSO is robust for small sample sizes and can be combined with imputation, random effects and logistic regression.

CHAPTER II: TREATMENT APPROACHES

CHAPTER III: RISK FACTORS

CHAPTER IV: RISK PREDICTORS

CHAPTER V: DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Summary of main findings

The thesis identified modifiable risk factors associated with major postoperative complications in the treatment of stage III and IV PIs in people with chronic SCI/D. The initial study showed that there are several treatment approaches for deep PIs in people with SCI/D [36]. The effectiveness of the treatment approaches was low because it was examined in one study [37]. Although there were some differences in the treatment approaches, the core of the approaches was similar [36]. The following twelve treatment elements were included in the approaches: PI classification, debridement, flap surgery, pressure relief and immobilization, infection control, treatment of osteomyelitis, wound conditioning, risk screening, therapies (physio-, occupational therapy and psychology), nutritional therapy, spasticity control and prevention and education [36]. In summary, possible risk factors for postoperative complications included person and PI characteristics, comorbidity characteristics, blood values and flap surgery characteristics.

In the second study, we examined these characteristics. It showed that stage IV PI, the absence of osteomyelitis, pathological blood concentrations of cystatin C, calcium and vitamin B12 as well as normal concentrations of HbA1c were statistically significantly associated with major postoperative complications among the BDA [38]. We hypothesized that the presence of osteomyelitis was a protective factor for major complications because of its individualized antibiotic treatment compared to standardized treatment in individuals without osteomyelitis [38]. In cases of pathological levels of cystatin C, calcium and vitamin B12 levels, delayed flap surgery should be considered in order to achieve normal blood levels at the time of flap surgery [38]. With regard to normal HbA1c levels, we assumed that the increased metabolism due to the PI might lower HbA1c concentrations such as sport or fasting [38].

In the third study C-reactive protein (CRP), eGFR according to the cystatin formula, sodium, vitamin B12 and vitamin D were predictive of major postoperative complications in the treatment of deep PIs in people with SCI/D at hospital admission among the BDA [39]. Although, these variables were statistically significant according to the Bayesian LASSO, their effects were not statistically significant [39]. While high eGFR, sodium and vitamin B12 had a negative effect, low CRP and high vitamin D had a positive effect on major postoperative complications [39]. We hypothesized that the CRP result could be due to an underlying osteomyelitis and the individualized antibiotic treatment [39]. Regarding vitamin D, we concluded that the substitution of deficiency among the BDA might be a confounding factor [39].

Implications for the Basel Decubitus Approach and future research

Based on the results of the three studies, there are recommendations regarding the non-modifiable and modifiable risk factors for the BDA and future research.

Non-modifiable risk factors

Stage IV PI, absence of osteomyelitis, low CRP and renal function at hospital admission were non-modifiable risk factors associated with major postoperative complications. Although, these factors cannot be changed by treatment, there are some recommendations for the BDA and future research.

Stage IV PI is more severe than stage III, involving muscle, bone, tendon or joint capsule [38]. Therefore, the awareness should be raised that people with a stage IV PI are more likely to have major postoperative complications. The treatment element of follow-up care and prophylaxis of the BDA should include prevention strategies to encourage people with SCI/D and PI to agree to early hospital admission if a PI is detected [38]. Early admission requires adequate resources for inpatient treatment [38]. Furthermore, the annual medical check-ups should include strategies for the prevention and early detection of PIs [40].

Regarding osteomyelitis, studies have shown that its presence is a risk factor for major postoperative complications [32, 41]. Conversely, in our study, the absence of osteomyelitis was associated with major postoperative complications, which is consistent with a previous study from our clinic by Rigazzi et al. [42]. Osteomyelitis can be difficult to diagnose and is likely underdiagnosed [41, 43, 44]. The absence of osteomyelitis might therefore be associated with major complications because osteomyelitis was not detected. In the cohort of Rigazzi et al. and in our cohort, osteomyelitis was diagnosed in 81% and 68%, respectively [42]. These findings are in line with the literature, where the osteomyelitis rate in people with deep PIs and SCI/D varies from 55% to 82% [45-47]. It is therefore reasonable to assume that osteomyelitis was adequately diagnosed by bone biopsy as well as bacteriological and histological examination. As already mentioned in the second study, individualized antibiotic treatment in people with osteomyelitis might have resulted in better infection control and therefore fewer major complications compared to individuals without osteomyelitis [36]. Conversely, osteomyelitis was not a risk predictor for major postoperative complications in the third study [39]. When two predictors are correlated, the logistic Bayesian LASSO analysis selects only one of the two predictors [48]. Individuals with osteomyelitis have higher CRP levels than those without osteomyelitis [42]. Because of this correlation, the logistic Bayesian LASSO analysis might have selected CRP instead of osteomyelitis. Therefore, it is recommended to consider

individualized antibiotic treatment also for individuals without osteomyelitis among the BDA [38]. To further understand the role of osteomyelitis, CRP and antibiotic treatment, a prospective cohort study should be conducted to observe major complication rates among the BDA using individualized antibiotic treatment for all individuals.

Regarding renal function, it is known that the risk of renal deterioration is increased in people with SCI/D [49]. It even increases with time after SCI/D [49]. In our studies, we found an association between renal function and major postoperative complications [38, 39]. This is in line with the literature [50, 51]. While in the second study cystatin C was associated with major postoperative complications, eGFR was a predictor. Treatment approaches consider renal function in the management of deep PIs in people with SCI/D [24, 36]. Cystatin C and eGFR are also already routinely collected at admission and during hospitalization among the BDA. This should continue to be done and renal function should be considered as a risk predictor for major postoperative complications.

Modifiable risk factors

Normal HbA1c, low calcium, low sodium, low vitamin B12 and high vitamin D were modifiable risk factors associated with major postoperative complications and can be addressed during the treatment. Therefore, following recommendations are made.

Regarding HbA1c levels, the assumption that an increased metabolism during a PI lowers HbA1c levels needs further investigation [38]. Therefore, studies observing HbA1c levels in individuals with SCI/D and deep PI are needed. HbA1c is not routinely assessed among the BDA. Therefore, due to too much missing data, we did not include HbA1c in the third study. Keys et al. found that HbA1c below 6% were associated with postoperative complications [33]. Thus, the BDA should include routinely testing for HbA1c levels at hospital admission. Furthermore, future studies should include HbA1c in risk prediction models.

Calcium was not mentioned in any of the treatment approaches [36]. As low calcium levels affect the wound healing process, it is recommended to substitute a calcium deficiency during treatment based on the findings [52]. To adequately address calcium deficiency further studies are needed to investigate the optimal calcium concentration for wound healing in SCI/D individuals with deep PI [52]. In addition, there is an interaction between calcium and vitamin D [53, 54]. Vitamin D plays a crucial role in calcium metabolism as it promotes intestinal absorption of calcium [54-56]. This correlation might be the reason why calcium was not a risk predictor for major postoperative complications, whereas vitamin D

was. Therefore, among the BDA it is recommended to continue to assess calcium at hospital admission.

Sodium and vitamin B12 deficiency are known to be associated with poor surgical outcomes or wound healing [9, 57]. Sodium deficiency is associated with a 2.5-fold increased risk of having a major complication after surgical procedures [57]. Based on the current knowledge of the role of sodium in major postoperative complications, sodium should continue to be monitored regularly during hospital stay among the BDA. In addition, diagnostic and therapeutic interventions should be performed in case of deficiency. In contrast to sodium, vitamin B12 levels are only assessed at hospital admission according to the BDA. Low vitamin B12 was mentioned as a risk factor in all three studies. It is therefore recommended to assess vitamin B12 levels and substitute in case of a deficiency [38].

In contrary to the literature, high vitamin D levels at hospital admission were positively associated with major postoperative complications [38]. Although, vitamin D supplementation was not mentioned in any of the treatment approaches, since 2016, the BDA includes substitution in case of deficiency [38, 39]. In individuals with high vitamin D levels, no supplementation was given and no follow up was performed. Therefore, we assumed that the treatment of vitamin D deficiency among the BDA confounded the results [39]. Another explanation might be smoking. The study by Yang et al. showed that smokers have lower vitamin D levels compared to non-smoker [58]. Yang et al., however, observed vitamin D levels in a non-SCI/D population [58]. This might be different in individuals with SCI/D due to their immobility. Smokers with SCI/D regularly go outside to smoke compared to non-smoker, resulting in sun exposure promoting vitamin D synthesis [59]. The little time spent outside for smoking might cause a difference in vitamin D levels. In fact, in our cohort, smokers had a mean vitamin D level of 64 nmol/l compared with 54 nmol/l in non-smoker. Cigarette smoking impairs flap healing in people with SCI/D and PI [7, 60]. Underlying smoking might be the reason why high vitamin D levels were associated with major postoperative complications. Based on the literature, smoking cessation prior to surgery is needed to reduce the risk of smoking-related complications [7, 37]. This is already applied through the BDA. It is recommended, to continue with the screening of vitamin D levels and substitution of deficiencies among the BDA. To better understand the positive association of high vitamin D levels on major complications, it is recommended to analyze vitamin D levels during hospital stay at different time points. Furthermore, studies on vitamin D levels and smoking in individuals with SCI/D are needed.

Finally, it remains unknown whether deficiencies of calcium, sodium, vitamin B12 and vitamin D were normalized at the time of flap surgery, based on the thesis. Therefore, it is

recommended to reassess levels at the time of flap surgery and to consider postponing surgery if deficiencies persist. However, substitution takes time to normalize blood levels. For example, vitamin D supplementation takes around twelve weeks to reach optimal vitamin D levels in deficient individuals [61]. About 63% of people in the third study cohort underwent flap surgery within three weeks of hospital admission. Delaying flap surgery until blood levels have normalized means a longer hospital stay. People with a deep PIs may have to wait in an outpatient setting or in another hospital before being admitted to a clinic specializing in the treatment of PIs. Therefore, an early assessment of blood levels prior to hospitalization in the outpatient setting should be considered. This would require appropriate communication between the hospitals or general practitioners. Although, this aspect might be difficult to implement, it is necessary to achieve optimal conditions for flap surgery by early substitution of deficiencies. Another option is regular blood testing as part of the annual medical examination before the onset of PI [40]. Regular monitoring of blood levels could prevent people with SCI/D from developing a deficiency in the first place.

Further implications

The first study showed that the evidence for the treatment approaches is limited [36]. Currently, the effectiveness of the BDA remains uncertain [36]. The thesis provides recommendations for adaptations of the approach. Therefore, future research should include a structured consensus conference where experts agree on the elements of the BDA based on the evidence [36]. Subsequently, prospective cohort studies with large sample sizes should be conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the approach [36]. This could be done by comparing outcomes such as complication rates, length of hospital stay and health care costs before and after the implementation of the revised BDA [36].

Based on the second and third study, there are other recommendation for future research. Some potential risk factors, such as the size of PI, periodic limb movements during sleep, or vascular status, could not be examined because their documentation was not standardized under the BDA [44]. Therefore, studies are needed to prospectively observe other potential risk factors. In addition, a pilot study using the risk prediction model from the third study at baseline is recommended for future research.

Limitations

One limitation of the first study is that there might be hospitals using a treatment approach for stage III and IV PIs in people with SCI/D that has not been published, has been published in a language other than English and German, or is available in a database other

than Medline and PubMed. Consequently, it is possible that a treatment approach was omitted. However, the results would probably remain the same because the treatment approaches were similar and comprehensive [36].

In addition, the retrospective nature of the second and third study on risk factors and risk predictors is another limitation. The quality of the standardized clinical documentation was limited [38]. This is because some documentation was missing and could not be determined retrospectively [38]. Moreover, both studies were exploratory, and we did not predefine a hypothesis about an effect because statistical power was not a primary concern [38, 62]. In the second study, the alpha error accumulation due to multiple testing was a limitation [38]. Nevertheless, the results are valuable because all the identified variables, except calcium, were also risk factors in the first or third study. In addition, calcium is also known to influence wound healing [52]. Another limitation of this thesis is that the risk factors and risk predictors were examined in a setting in where the BDA is used. However, most clinics specializing in the management of deep PIs in people with SCI/D have similar treatment approaches and might therefore be applicable [36].

Conclusion

This thesis presents, for the first time, modifiable risk factors associated with major postoperative complications in the treatment of stage III and IV PIs in individuals with chronic SCI/D. We found that among the BDA stage IV PI, the absence of osteomyelitis, low CRP, low renal function, normal HbA1c, low calcium, low sodium, low vitamin B12 and high vitamin D were positively associated with major postoperative complications.

Based on these findings, four major adjustments to the BDA are recommended. First, regarding the treatment element of follow-up care and prophylaxis, individuals should be made aware that stage IV PI is associated with major postoperative complications and should therefore be encouraged to seek early hospitalization in case of a further PI. Second, the antibiotic treatment should be individualized not only for those with osteomyelitis but also for those without. Third, HbA1c levels should be routinely tested among the BDA at hospital admission. And fourth, calcium, sodium, vitamin B12 and vitamin D levels should be re-assessed at the time of flap surgery to consider postponing surgery in the case of deficiencies. In terms of coordinated care, early assessment of blood levels and treatment of deficiencies prior to hospitalization in an outpatient setting should be considered. In this way, optimal conditions could be achieved prior to surgery.

There are also some implications for further research. Studies should be conducted to assess the effectiveness of treatment approaches. Furthermore, studies are needed to observe complication rates among the BDA using individualized antibiotic treatment for individuals with and without osteomyelitis. Research should also focus on HbA1c levels in SCI/D individuals with deep PIs and include HbA1c in future risk models. To adequately treat calcium deficiency, research is needed to define optimal calcium levels during treatment of deep PIs. In addition, research on vitamin D levels and smoking in individuals with deep PIs and SCI/D is needed. Finally, future research should also focus on other possible risk factors that were not observed in this thesis, such as the size of the PI.

The results of this thesis are an impetus for improving the treatment of stage III and IV PIs in people with SCI/D in order to reduce major postoperative complication rates and ultimately improve the quality of life of people with SCI/D and stage III and IV PI in the future.

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Supplementary material of chapter II**Table 1. PRISMA-ScR checklist**

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a scoping review.	Title
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary that includes (as applicable): background, objectives, eligibility criteria, sources of evidence, charting methods, results, and conclusions that relate to the review questions and objectives.	p. 2; Background, objectives, methods, results, conclusion
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known. Explain why the review questions/objectives lend themselves to a scoping review approach.	p. 3 et seq.; Introduction, last part
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the questions and objectives being addressed with reference to their key elements (e.g., population or participants, concepts, and context) or other relevant key elements used to conceptualize the review questions and/or objectives.	p. 3 et seq.; Introduction, last part
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists; state if and where it can be accessed (e.g., a Web address); and if available, provide registration information, including the registration number.	p. 4; First section, last sentence
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify characteristics of the sources of evidence used as eligibility criteria (e.g., years considered, language, and publication status), and provide a rationale.	p. 4; Literature search strategy and study selection and appraisal
Information sources	7	Describe all information sources in the search (e.g., databases with dates of coverage and contact with authors to identify additional sources), as well as the date the most recent search was executed.	p. 4; Literature search strategy
Search	8	Present the full electronic search strategy for at least 1 database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	p. 4; Literature search strategy
Selection of sources of evidence	9	State the process for selecting sources of evidence (i.e., screening and eligibility) included in the scoping review.	p. 4 et seq; Selection process, data synthesis and level of evidence
Data charting process	10	Describe the methods of charting data from the included sources of evidence (e.g., calibrated forms or forms that have been tested by the team before their use, and whether data charting was done independently or in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	Not applicable
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought and any assumptions and simplifications made.	p. 5; Selection process data

SECTION	ITEM	PRISMA-ScR CHECKLIST ITEM	REPORTED ON PAGE #
			synthesis and level of evidence
Critical appraisal of individual sources of evidence	12	If done, provide a rationale for conducting a critical appraisal of included sources of evidence; describe the methods used and how this information was used in any data synthesis (if appropriate).	Not applicable
Synthesis of results	13	Describe the methods of handling and summarizing the data that were charted.	p. 5; Selection process data synthesis and level of evidence
RESULTS			
Selection of sources of evidence	14	Give numbers of sources of evidence screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally using a flow diagram.	p. 6; Study selection
Characteristics of sources of evidence	15	For each source of evidence, present characteristics for which data were charted and provide the citations.	Table 1; Characterization of eligible studies
Critical appraisal within sources of evidence	16	If done, present data on critical appraisal of included sources of evidence (see item 12).	Not applicable
Results of individual sources of evidence	17	For each included source of evidence, present the relevant data that were charted that relate to the review questions and objectives.	p. 6 et seq.
Synthesis of results	18	Summarize and/or present the charting results as they relate to the review questions and objectives.	p. 6 et seq.
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	19	Summarize the main results (including an overview of concepts, themes, and types of evidence available), link to the review questions and objectives, and consider the relevance to key groups.	p. 13; Stage III and IV PI treatment approaches
Limitations	20	Discuss the limitations of the scoping review process.	Not applicable
Conclusions	21	Provide a general interpretation of the results with respect to the review questions and objectives, as well as potential implications and/or next steps.	p. 16; Conclusion
FUNDING			
Funding	22	Describe sources of funding for the included sources of evidence, as well as sources of funding for the scoping review. Describe the role of the funders of the scoping review.	p. 17; Funding
<p>PRISMA-ScR = Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews.</p> <p>From: Tricco AC, Lillie E, Zarin W, O'Brien KK, Colquhoun H, Levac D, et al. PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMAScR): Checklist and Explanation. <i>Ann Intern Med.</i> 2018;169:467–473.</p>			

Table 2. Search strategy

PubMed	Medline
(("pressure ulcer"[Mesh]) OR ("pressure injur*") OR ("pressure ulcer*") OR ("pressure sore*") OR ("bedsore*") OR ("bed sore*") OR (decubitus)) AND (("treatment concept*") OR ("treatment*")) AND (("Spinal Cord Injuries"[Mesh]) OR ("spinal cord injur*") OR ("spinal injur*") OR ("sci") OR ("spinal lesion*")) AND ((humans[Filter]) AND (english[Filter] OR german[Filter]) AND (1990:2021[pdat]))	<p>1 pressure injur*.mp. (1425)</p> <p>2 exp Pressure Ulcer/ or pressure ulcer*.mp. (15439)</p> <p>3 pressure sore*.mp. (3147)</p> <p>4 bedsore*.mp.(549)</p> <p>5 decubitus.mp. (5611)</p> <p>6 treatment concept*.mp. (2823)</p> <p>7 treatment*.mp. (5495955)</p> <p>8 exp Spinal Cord Injuries/ (52309)</p> <p>9 spinal cord injur*.mp. (53556)</p> <p>10 Spinal injur*.mp. (13801)</p> <p>11 spinal lesion*.mp. (1956)</p> <p>12 1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 (21024)</p> <p>13 6 or 7 (5495955)</p> <p>14 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 (74850)</p> <p>15 12 and 13 and 14 (560)</p> <p>16 limit 15 to yr="1990 - 2021" (493)</p>

Table 3. PICOS framework

Criteria	Description
Population	Individuals aged ≥ 18 years with SCI/D and deep PI stage III or IV over ischium, trochanter or sacrum and without multiple sclerosis, malignant disease or local skin disease
Interventions	Various treatment elements and interventions of multidisciplinary and surgical treatment approaches for deep PI stage III or IV over ischium, trochanter or sacrum in the acute or rehabilitation setting during the chronic phase of SCI/D
Comparators	No comparator, assessments of all interventions of the treatment of deep PI
Outcomes	Ensuring wound treatment with best outcome as possible
Study design	All

PI: pressure injury; SCI/D: spinal cord injury or spinal cord disorder

Table 4. Assessment of evidence level according to the modified Sackett Scale

First author, year	Level of evidence*
CSCM, 2014	5
Jordan, 2017	5
Kreutzträger, 2018	2
Kruger, 2013	5
Ljung, 2017	5
Meier, 2019	5
Rieger, 2007	5
Rosin, 2020	5
Shenaq, 1990	5
Sørensen, 2004	5
Tadiparthi, 2016	2
Thomas, 2001	5

*according to Sackett Scale

Table 5. Results of osteomyelitis and infection control

Reference	Bacterial load diagnostic	OM diagnostic	Treatment without OM	Treatment with OM	Type of administration
CSCM, 2014	Quantitative culture to diagnose infection	Bone biopsy during if bone is extended		Antibiotic treatment of 4 to 6 weeks	Parenteral
Jordan, 2017		bone biopsy during if bone is extended		Has to be addressed with a radical debridement prior to flap surgery; 6 weeks of antibiotic therapy	Intravenous antibiotics if OM for 6 weeks in an outpatient setting prior to flap closure; local AB is not indicated
Kreutzträger, 2018	Wound swabs for bacterial spectrum and resistogram				Systemic oral or parenteral antibiotics for at least 14 days based on a resistogram
Kruger, 2013		Bone biopsy as gold standard	The deep culture and histopathology of a bone biopsy dictates the length of antibiotic treatment	6 weeks antibiotic treatment of acute osteomyelitis	Intravenous antibiotics
Ljung, 2016			Antibiotic treatment of 1 week	Antibiotic treatment of 1 week	The first 3 days intravenous antibiotics
Meier, 2019	Samples taken during debridement or flap surgery	Bone biopsy during debridement or flap surgery if bone is extended		Antibiotic treatment of 6 to 8 weeks	
Rieger, 2007	Bacteriological diagnosis	Bone biopsy	Postsurgical antibiotic treatment should last 5 days	Has to be addressed with a radical debridement prior to flap surgery; antibiotic treatment of 3 months	
Rosin, 2020		Diagnosis relies on bone biopsy and culture		Antibiotics for 6 weeks	
Shenaq, 1990			Postsurgical antibiotic treatment of 10 to 14 days	Antibiotics for 6 weeks	
Sørensen, 2004	Swab samples taken during debridement	Prefer bone biopsy during debridement if bone is extended rather than non-invasive procedures	Postsurgical antibiotic treatment should last 5 to 7 days	Antibiotic treatment of 3 months	Intravenously for the first 2 weeks, later orally; local AB is not indicated
Tadiparthi, 2016	preoperative wound cultures or microorganisms found in the bone biopsy	Bone biopsy during debridement	Antibiotics until suction drain removal, approximately 2 weeks after reconstruction	Antibiotic treatment of 6 to 12 weeks	
Thomas, 2001		Bone biopsy is the most useful test			

AB: antibiotics; CSCM: Consortium for Spinal Cord Medicine; OM: osteomyelitis; PI: pressure injury.

Table 6. Results of flap surgery techniques

First author, year	Ischial PI	Sacral PI	Trochanteric PI	Not location specific
CSCM, 2014				Myocutaneous and fasciocutaneous flaps have superior success rates a
Jordan, 2017	Bilateral muscle advancement flap			
Kreutzträger, 2018	VY-hamstrings, myo- or fasciocutaneous and myocutaneous gluteus maximus inferior flap	Fasciocutaneous gluteus maximus, uni- or bilateral and rotation or VY flap	Tensor fascia latae flap	
Kruger, 2013	Gluteus maximus rotation, gracilis, VY hamstring advancement, inferior gluteal perforator, medial thigh fasciocutaneous or posterior thigh fasciocutaneous flap	Gluteus maximus or superior gluteal artery perforator flap	Tensor fascia latae rotation or VY flap or an anterior lateral thigh flap	
Ljung, 2017				Musculocutaneous local flap
Meier, 2019	Posterior thigh flap	Gluteal rotation flap	Tensor fascia latae flap	
Rieger, 2007	Posterior thigh flap	Gluteal rotation flap	Tensor fascia latae flap	
Shenaq, 1990				Skin graf, skin flaps, muscle flaps, musculocutaneous flaps, neurovascular flaps, free flaps
Sørensen, 2004	Flap based on the hamstrings, only secondarily, myocutaneous gluteus maximus flap	Gluteus maximus myocutaneous flap	Tensor fascia latae flap	
Tadiparthi, 2016	Gluteal myocutaneous rotation flap	Gluteal myocutaneous advancement flap	Tensor fascia latae advancement flap	
Thomas, 2001				Myocutaneous flap

CSCM: Consortium for Spinal Cord Medicine; PI: pressure injury.

Table 7. Results of blood and nutritional parameter recommended in the studies

First author, year	Amino acids	Cholesterol	Copper	Creatinine	CRP	FBG	Folate/Folic acid	Haematocrit	Haemoglobin	LFT	Magnesium	Nitrogen	OM3FAs	Potassium	Prealbumin	Sodium	TLC	Total protein	Transferrin	Vitamin A	Vitamin B12	Vitamin C	Zinc	
CSCM, 2014	+				o	+	+	+	+	+					+		+	+		+	+	-	+	
Kreutzträger, 2018														+		+								
Kruger, 2013		+		+								+			+				+					
Rieger, 2007							+						+				+	+			+		+	
Shenaq, 1990											+											+	+	
Thomas, 2001		-	-						-	-		-					-	-				+	+	

BMI: body mass index; CSCM: Consortium for Spinal Cord Medicine; FBG: fasting blood glucose; LFT: liver function test; OM3FAs: omega-3-fatty acids; TLC: total lymphocyte count; +: recommended; -: not recommended; o: only for the interpretation of albumin/prealbumin.

Table 8. Methods according to PRISMA-ScR checklist

First author, year	Protocol and registration	Eligibility criteria	Information sources	Search	Selection of sources of evidence	Data charting process	Data items	Synthesis of results
Thomas, 2001	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

√: all items were adequately addressed; x: one or more items were not adequately addressed.

Table 9. Methods according to STROBE checklist

First author, year	Study design	Setting	Participants	Variables	Data sources/ measurement	Bias	Study size	Quantitative variables	Statistical methods
Jordan, 2017*	√	x	x	x	x	x	√	√	x
Kreutzträger, 2019*	√	x	√	x	x	x	x	x	x
Ljung, 2017*	x	x	√	x	x	x	x	x	x
Meier, 2019*	√	√	√	x	x	x	x	x	x
Tadiparthi, 2016**	x	√	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

*: STROBE checklist for cross-sectional studies; **: STROBE checklist for cohort studies; √: all items were adequately addressed; x: one or more items were not adequately addressed.

Table 10. Methods according to DELBI checklist

Reference	CSCM*, 2014
Methodological rigor of development	Points**
Systematic methods were used to search for evidence.	2
The criteria for selecting the evidence are clearly described.	3
The methods used for formulating the recommendations are clearly described.	2
Health benefits, side effects and risks have been considered in formulating the recommendations.	2
There is an explicit link between the recommendations and the supporting evidence.	3
The guideline has been externally reviewed by experts prior to its publication.	3
A procedure for updating the guideline is provided.	1
*Consortium for Spinal Cord Medicine; **achieved points out of a maximum of 4 possible points.	

Appendix B: Supplementary material of chapter III**Table 1. Number of PI during the observation period**

Number of PI during observation period	Number of individuals N=149 n (%)	Total cases N=220 n (%)
1	103 (69)	103 (47)
2	30 (20)	60 (27)
3	12 (8)	36 (16)
4	2 (1)	8 (4)
5	1 (1)	5 (2)
6	0	0
7	0	0
8	1 (1)	8 (4)

Table 2. Characteristics of major complications

Type of complication N=220	Major complications N=42 n (%)
Wound dehiscence	25 (11)
Wound infection	1 (0)
Bleeding or hematoma	4 (2)
Necrosis	11 (5)
Unknown	1 (0)

Table 3. Statistically significant blood values categorized in levels, by complications

Blood values (reference value)	Total N=220 n (%)	Major complications	
		No N=178 n (%)	Yes N=42 n (%)
Cystatin C (0,61-0,95 mg/l)			
Deficit	0	0	0
Norm	68 (31)	60 (88)	8 (12)
Excess	124 (56)	93 (75)	31 (25)
Calcium (2.2-2.6 mmol/L)			
Deficit	29 (13)	20 (69)	9 (31)
Norm	68 (31)	58 (85)	10 (15)
Excess	0	0	0
HbA1c (4.8-5.9%)			
Deficit	37 (58)	34 (92)	3 (8)
Norm	14 (22)	9 (64)	5 (36)
Excess	12 (19)	9 (75)	3 (25)
Vitamin B12 (200-1000 ng/L)			
Deficit	25 (11)	15 (60)	10 (40)
Norm	88 (40)	75 (85)	13 (15)
Excess	4 (2)	3 (75)	1 (25)

Appendix C: Supplementary material of chapter IV**Traces and Autocorrelation**

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